

Enhancing Undergraduate Learning through Library Audio-Visual Resources: Evidence from Katsina State Universities

¹Samaila Sani ²Abbas Hamisu PhD ³Danladi Garba Duru

¹Katsina State College of Health Sciences and Technology; ²Federal University of Education, Zaria;

³Federal University Dutsinma

¹babajonbry@gmail.com

²abbascln@gmail.com

³dgduru@fudutsinma.edu.ng

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19437825>

Abstract

Enhancing Undergraduate Learning through Library Audio-Visual Resources: Evidence from Katsina State Universities. The objectives of the study include determining the availability of library audio-visual resources to support learning activities in Katsina State universities. To examine the perceived benefits of the use of library audio-visual resources by undergraduate students in their learning activities in Katsina State universities. The research design employed for this study was a descriptive survey, and two universities in Katsina State were selected, namely, Federal University Dutsinma (FUDMA) and Umaru Musa Yar'adua University Katsina (UMYUK). Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of simple percentages of responses on demographic data, and means for the research questions. The study revealed that digital audio-visual resources (computers, online databases, e-books) are generally more available than traditional ones (CDs/DVDs). The study also revealed that audio-visual resources are most valued for research among others.

Keyword: Availability, Use, Audio Visual Resources, Learning Activities, Undergraduate Students, Katsina State

Introduction

Audio-visual technologies remain highly relevant because they are the primary medium for generating, processing, and consuming massive amounts of information. The use and development of audio-visual resources in Nigerian Institutions are increasingly accepted because the role of audio-visual resources in enhancing the pedagogical process cannot be overemphasised; that is, classroom teaching and learning activities have become increasingly pivotal. Traditional teaching methods, primarily focused on lectures and textbooks, often fall short in engaging today's learners, who are accustomed to modern, interactive, and media-rich experiences outside the classroom. The audio-visual resources bring new depth and dimension to learning, and, on their own, have proven effective in capturing students' attention, making complex concepts more understandable, and increasing information retention. Within the Nigerian tertiary education cycle, formal education is primarily provided for individuals who have completed a secondary education. According to Onuoha and Chukwueke (2020), a series of transformations has occurred in the Nigerian school system with the introduction of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in teaching and learning. They also observe a constant increase in the number of pupils and students enrolled in tertiary institutions, which means the use of ICTs in teaching and learning cannot be overemphasised. And for an effective teaching and learning environment to take place, libraries play an important role in providing tools that aid learning, beyond reading text. Among such tools provided by libraries are audio-visual information resources.

The audio-visual (AV) resources remain powerful tools for enhancing learning activities in university libraries. Audio resources appeal to the sense of hearing, while visual resources appeal to the sense of sight. These resources are designed to support learners' learning activities and enhance students' understanding of the subject content. Audio-visual media, according to Dewi, Hudiyono, and Mulawarman (2018), involves listening and viewing processes used in learning activities such as movies, videos, television programmes and sound slides. This is supported by Andrew, Dewa Putu (2020), who opined that audio-visual is a medium that combines audio and visual media, using the senses of sight and hearing as mediators in the transmission of information. These audio-visual media are available online as sound effects (audio) and images (visuals) produced during a play through various digital applications. Moreover, they are not entirely dependent on word understanding (Riyanto & Asmara, 2018).

Learning that utilises audio-visual media is enhanced when compared to conventional media (Isna Nadifah Nur Fauziah et al., 2023). A study by Natoli (2011) stressed that audio-visual resources are important in the teaching and learning processes because “having seen something, most people remember, for whatever that thing was, it raises an image at a mere mention and can be talked about freely”. Additionally, the world is becoming more digitalised, paving the way to manual methods of teaching and learning using the chalkboard (Onuoha & Chukwueke, 2020). Examples of audio-visual resources formats are videos, films, animations, audio recordings, presentations, computers, films, slides, transparencies, projectors, photographs, maps, posters, charts, audio/video CDs, tape recorder/player, including olden days video cassette recorder (VCR) & video cassette player (VCP), and Xerox machine, among others. Today, interactive media or interactive multimedia also form part of these resources, which are perceived as engaging multiple senses to enhance understanding and retention.

Audio-visual learning materials are essential as visual and auditory tools that are presented simultaneously and enable interactive, entertaining, and effective teaching (Et al., 2021). Consequently, Rahmatullah, Inanna, and Ampa (2020) said that audio-visual enriches the learning environment, promotes learning, exploration, and discovery, and encourages learners to speak and express their thoughts. Not only can those messages from an audio-visual medium be clearly conveyed both orally and in writing without limiting space, time, or meaning.

Despite the significance of audio-visual resources in tertiary education, preliminary observations indicate that most university libraries in Nigeria own limited or no audio-visual resources. This could be assumed and tied to the poor funding of university education in Nigeria, as most of these ICT gadgets are very expensive. On the other hand, it could be speculated that some students in Nigerian universities are not ICT-inclined and exhibit techno-phobia in some cases. To whatever extent, speculations or assumptions, unproven empirically, cannot be used to affirm the availability and utilisation of audio-visual resources to enhance learning activities in universities across Nigeria. Therefore, this study seeks to examine the availability and utilisation of audio-visual resources to enhance learning activities in universities in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Objectives

The main study objective was to examine the availability and use of audio-visuals to enhance learning activities in Katsina State universities. Specifically, the objectives of the study were:

1. To examine the availability of library audio-visual resources for improved learning activities in Katsina State universities.
2. To examine the perceived benefits in the use of library audio-visual resources by undergraduate students in their learning activities in Katsina State universities.

3. To uncover the challenges facing the effective utilization of library audio visual resources by undergraduate students in Katsina State universities.

Literature Review

The learning process is crucial at all levels of educational development, and the best methods must be used to enhance effective learning. It is for this reason that some scholars have taken the step of writing on the use of audiovisual resources as an important means of enhancing learning outcomes. The influence of audio-visual resources in promoting students' learning activities cannot be overstressed. Availability and utilisation of audio-visuals simply mean the presentation of knowledge to be gained through hearing, seeing, and a combination of the two. On the benefits of audiovisuals, Patil (2012) reveals that mere chalk-and-talk does not help learning in the contemporary world, and this is why Wahlig (2012) observed that audiovisual resources supplement oral and written information with graphical representations and interactive, varied learning experiences for students.

Therefore, incorporating audio-visual resources into a classroom lesson enhances the learning experience, making it more conceptual and effective, increasing students' motivation and capturing their attention. Thus, scholars have affirmed that these tools go beyond traditional teaching methods. According to Mayer's Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning, individuals process information more effectively when it is presented simultaneously in auditory and visual forms (Mayer, 2009). Chukwueke and Oluwabunmithe (2022) studied the availability and utilisation of audio-visuals for teaching and learning in Nigerian universities, and they came to observe that the majority of the respondents were used to audio-visuals, and above average, the respondents affirmed that audio-visuals make their learning very easy, and they reduce the cost of acquiring learning resources. In a similar finding, Sword (2021) noted the benefits of audio-visual resources towards captivating students' attention and curiosity. Obviously, traditional verbal lessons can usually be boring for students and may obstruct their learning experience.

Regarding audio-visuals, the dynamic nature of videos has been awesome. Berk (2009) found that multimedia presentations, such as videos, animations, and sound, are effective tools for enhancing learners' interest. It's the multimedia's multisensory nature that makes it appealing in sustaining students' focus and motivation over time. For example, a well-structured video that combines explanatory narration with visuals can make complex topics more approachable and memorable. This is why Raudatussolihah (2022) believe that audiovisual resources improve students' understanding.

Additionally, Rahamatullah, Inanna, and Ampa (2020) stress that the use of attractive media increases students' attention to learning. This means that, to facilitate the implementation of learning processes both online and offline, the utilisation of visual and aural media is essential. Indrawati, Ninghardjanti, Dirgatama, and Wirawan (2022) studied the effectiveness of audio-visual hands-on learning in vocational secondary schools. The results show that Audio-visual based practical learning enhances students' learning. Abubakar, Abdullah, Ali, and Kabir (2018) examine teachers' perspectives on the use of visual audio materials in teaching and learning. They opined that Visual and aural learning aids encourage learning and enhance students' comprehension.

Because of the characteristics of audio-visuals, these resources pose some challenges, and these challenges have been documented by various authors. According to Aloraini (2012), issues such as equipment malfunctions, inadequate technical support, and inconsistent internet connectivity sometimes disrupt the learning process. These are referred to as technical challenges, and they not only affect the accessibility of the educational content but also diminish the overall effectiveness of audio-visual resources. Kay et al.

(2009) stressed on insufficient professional development in the use of multimedia. They observed that, the lack of proper training significantly limits, for example, teachers’ ability to align audio-visual resources with the curriculum’s learning objectives. This means that, with inadequate knowledge or understanding of how to integrate these tools meaningfully, educators may struggle to use them in ways that enhance learning. Furthermore, Oyewale (2021) also explained that among the challenges towards integrating technology in learning are insufficient preparation time, lack of technology resources, low level of confidence and competence of teachers in the use of ICT, lack of technical support, tools, and lack of motivation. Consequently, the study by Ojobor, Babarinde and Fagbemi (2020) uncovered that insufficient funding, lack of competent teachers, lack of awareness, erratic power supply, lack of space, and non-availability of instructional resources are among the contributing factors to the non-use of audio-visual resources in learning.

Methodology

The research design employed for this study is a descriptive survey to assess the availability and use of library audio-visual resources across universities in Kastina State. There were two selected universities in the state: Federal University Dutsinma (FUDMA) and Ummaru Musa Yar’adua University, Katsina (UMYUK). The population of the study were the undergraduate students in the department of library and information science in the two universities. The student population was as follows: 182 from FUDMA and 107 from UMYUK. Purposive sampling was used to strategically select the final-year students, that is, 400-level students, as opposed to 100-300-level students. The researchers believed that final-year students, by experience, have been familiarised with the use of the university’s libraries. Yamane's (1967) sample size formula, with a 0.05 Margin of Error and 95% confidence, was used to obtain sample sizes for the students: 126 for FUDMA and 85 for UMYUK. However, the sampled students were randomly selected using random sampling at each institution. The data collection instrument was a questionnaire, validated by experts in the library field. A sample of 10% of the sampled students from FUDMA and UMYUK was used to obtain the reliability of the questionnaire, and Cronbach’s Alpha Coefficient revealed 0.68 on the availability of library audio-visual resources, 0.69 on the perceived benefits in the use of library audio-visual resources, and 0.70 on the challenges facing the effective utilisation of library audio-visual resources. Data collected were analysed using descriptive statistics of simple percentages of responses on demographic data, and means for the research questions.

Table 1: Audio-visual Resources Available in the Library

Availability of Audio-Visual Resources	HA	A	HNA	NA	NS	Total	Mean	Decision
Projectors	58	61	35	28	4	188	3.57	Agreed
Television Sets	55	58	45	25	5	188	3.71	Agreed
Computers with multimedia Access	65	60	37	23	3	188	3.86	Agreed
Educational CDs/DVDs	27	30	55	61	15	188	2.96	Disagreed
e-Books/e-Journals	60	61	34	28	5	188	3.76	Agreed
Online Databases	65	60	37	26	-	188	3.87	Agreed

Key: HA=Highly Available, A=Available, HNA=Highly Not Available, NA= Not Available, NS=Not Sure

From the table above, respondents reveal that the most available audio-visual resources are online databases, with the highest mean of 3.87, and computers with multimedia access, with a strong presence of both "Highly Available" (98) and "Available" (87). This results in a mean value of 3.86. The least

available resource is educational CDs/DVDs (Mean = 2.96), with high counts of "Highly Not Available" (92) and "Not Available" (95). Moderately available resources include e-Books/e-Journals (Mean = 3.76), television sets (Mean = 3.71), and projectors (Mean = 3.57). These show balanced availability but still some gaps. Projectors (Mean = 3.73) suggest decent availability, but 63 respondents marked them as "Not Available," indicating inconsistency. In summary, digital resources (computers, online databases, e-books) are generally more available than traditional ones (CDs/DVDs). This signals a clear shift toward modern, online-based learning tools. CDs/DVDs are becoming obsolete in educational settings, while computers and online databases form the backbone of multimedia learning. Projectors and TVs remain important but show mixed availability, possibly due to maintenance or distribution issues.

Table 2: Purpose of Using Audio-Visual Resources

Purpose of Using Audio-Visual Resources	SA	A	SD	DA	UD	TOTAL	MEAN	Decision
Class Assignment	59	60	29	33	7	188	3.69	Agreed
Research Work	60	61	34	28	5	188	3.76	Agreed
Group Discussion/Presentation	32	37	48	57	14	188	3.08	Agreed
Personal Use	60	59	27	34	8	188	3.68	Agreed
Project Work	60	61	35	28	5	188	3.76	Agreed

Key: SA=Strongly Agree, A Agree, SD=Strongly Disagree, DA= Disagree, UD=Undecided

Table 3 shows the purpose of using audio-visual resources in research work and project work, each with the highest mean score of 3.76. This indicates that audio-visual resources are most valued for research and projects, probably because they offer clarity, evidence, and a deeper understanding. The second highest is class assignments (3.69), suggesting that assignments also benefit from AV resources as they often require creativity, presentation, and detailed explanations. Moderate importance is given to class and personal use (3.68) and (3.53), meaning students find AV resources useful for personal enrichment, but not as strongly as for research. The lowest mean (3.08) was observed for group discussion/presentation; surprisingly, AV resources are less used, possibly because discussions rely more on verbal interaction and collaboration rather than external media.

Table 3: Extent to which Audio-Visual Resources Enhanced Learning Activities

Audio Resources	Visual Resources	VGE	G E	ME	LE	NE	Total	Mean	Decision
Projectors		50	58	33	42	5	188	3.56	Agreed
Television Sets		49	57	42	37	3	188	3.59	Agreed
Computers with multimedia Access		60	61	34	28	5	188	3.61	Agreed
Educational CDs/DVDs		30	38	45	62	13	188	2.72	Disagreed
e-Books/e-Journals		58	63	40	27	-	188	3.66	Agreed
Databases		62	56	41	27	2	188	3.79	Agreed

Key: VGE=Very Great Extent, GE=Great Extent, ME=Moderate Extent, LE=Low Extent, NE=No

Table 4 shows that Databases (3.79) have the highest-rated mean, indicating a strong reliance on structured digital resources. Meanwhile, computers with e-Books/e-Journals (3.66) remain essential for modern learning. Multimedia access (3.61) is widely accepted, reflecting the digital shift in education. Television Sets (3.59) are still relevant, particularly in blended learning environments. Projectors (3.56) are moderately valued, suggesting they are useful for traditional classroom presentations. Educational CDs/DVDs (2.72) were rejected, highlighting their obsolescence in today’s digital learning environment. Digital resources dominate; this indicates that databases, e-books, and computers are the backbone of modern education, while traditional tools like projectors and TVs continue to play a role, albeit less centrally. CDs/DVDs no longer meet the needs of learners.

Table 4: Extent to which Learning Activities are Most Improved by Audio-Visual Resources

Learning Activities	SA	A	SD	DA	UD	Total	Mean	Decision
Preparing assignment	53	58	42	30	5	188	3.66	Agreed
Understanding lectures	60	59	37	32	-	188	3.78	Agreed
Conducting research	58	56	37	31	6	252	3.68	Agreed
Group collaboration	42	46	55	40	5	188	3.42	Agreed
Exam preparation	42	47	55	40	4	188	3.44	Agreed

Key: SA=Strongly Agree, A Agree, SD=Strongly Disagree, DA= Disagree, UD=Undecided

Table 5 reveals that understanding lectures (Mean = 3.78), indicating that audio-visual resources are most effective and have the highest impact. Students find lectures easier to grasp when supported with visuals and audio aids. While conducting research with a mean value of 3.68, preparing assignments has a mean value of 3.66, and exam preparation (Mean = 3.44), this suggests that AV resources moderately improve these activities, assisting students in organising and recalling information better. The least effective is group collaboration (Mean = 3.42), as AV resources are less helpful here. This likely indicates that research often requires deeper reading and analysis, while collaboration relies more on interpersonal interaction than on AV tools.

Table 5: Challenges in Using Audio-Visual Resources

Challenges using AV	SA	A	SD	DA	UD	TOTAL	MEAN	DECISION
Limited availability	42	46	55	40	5	188	3.42	Agree
Poor maintenance	60	61	34	28	5	188	3.61	Agree
Lack of technical support	53	64	32	35	4	188	3.67	Agree
Inadequate awareness/training	55	64	37	30	2	188	3.74	Strongly Agree
Power supply issues	60	53	42	30	3	188	3.73	Strongly Agree

Key: SA=Strongly Agree, A=Agree, SD=Strongly Disagree, D=Disagree, UD=Undecided

Table 6 highlights the most significant challenges, starting with inadequate awareness and training (Mean = 3.74), which is the biggest obstacle. Many users lack proper training or awareness of how to use AV tools effectively, especially in areas with power supply issues (Mean = 3.73), presenting a critical infrastructural challenge, particularly in regions with unstable electricity. Moderate challenges include poor maintenance (Mean = 3.61), as AV equipment often suffers from neglect, reducing usability, and a

lack of technical support (Mean = 3.67), where the absence of skilled personnel causes delays in troubleshooting and repairs. This remains a systemic issue that hampers AV integration in education. Least severe, but still noteworthy, are limited availability (Mean = 3.42). While availability is an issue, it is less urgent compared to training and power supply concerns. Essentially, even when AV tools are available, poor upkeep and a lack of technical support diminish their effectiveness.

Discussion

The study investigated Enhancing Undergraduate Learning through Library Audio-Visual Resources: Evidence from Katsina State Universities. Findings from the study revealed that digital resources (computers, online databases, e-books) are generally more available than traditional ones (CDs/DVDs). This, in essence, indicates a clear shift towards modern, online-based learning tools. CDs/DVDs are becoming obsolete in educational settings, while computers and online databases are the backbone, possibly due to maintenance or distribution issues. The study also revealed that audio-visual resources are most valued for research, likely because they provide clarity, evidence, and a deeper understanding. Students find AV resources useful for projects, as they often require creativity, presentation, and detailed explanations, as well as assignments and personal enrichment. Regarding the extent to which students use AV resources, the study revealed that computers with multimedia access (3.72) remain essential for modern learning. E-books and e-journals (3.70) have strong acceptance, reflecting the digital shift in education. Television sets (3.64) are still relevant, especially in blended learning environments. Projectors (3.38) are moderately valued, making them useful for traditional classroom presentations. Educational CDs/DVDs (2.18) were rejected.

The study also revealed how AV resources enhance students' learning, with results showing that understanding lectures is easier when supported by visuals and audio resources. When preparing assignments and for exam preparation (Mean = 3.38 each), this indicates that AV resources moderately improve these activities, helping students organise and recall information more effectively. The findings support those of Chukwueke and Oluwabunmi (2022), who reported that the respondents in their research affirmed that audio-visuals make learning very easy and reduce the cost of acquiring learning resources.

The study ultimately identified challenges in using AV resources among undergraduate students, ranging from inadequate awareness and training (Mean = 3.78) to power supply issues (Mean = 3.73), poor maintenance (Mean = 3.58), lack of technical support (Mean = 3.43), and limited availability (Mean = 3.38). In essence, while availability remains an issue, it is less critical compared to training and power supply. This suggests that even when AV tools are accessible, poor maintenance and the absence of technical support hinder their effectiveness. These findings are consistent with those of Indrawati, Ninghardjanti, Dirgatama, and Wirawan (2022) in their study on the effectiveness of audio-visual hands-on learning in vocational secondary schools. The results indicate that audio-visual practical learning enhances students' learning experience. Additionally, Ojobor, Babarinde, and Fagbemi (2020) found that factors such as insufficient funding, lack of competent teachers, lack of awareness, erratic power supply, limited space, and non-availability of instructional resources contribute to the underuse of audio-visual resources in learning.

Conclusion

The study concludes that, although AV resources are available in the institutions examined, they remain valuable for learning and enhance research and project work by providing clarity, evidence, and deeper understanding. It also indicates that online databases, e-books/journals, and television sets are widely accepted, reflecting the digital shift in education. Additionally, the study found that the use of AV

resources faces some challenges, including low awareness, a lack of technical support, and limited availability, among others.

Recommendations

However, the study recommends the following.

1. The library management should consider making AV resources more available since there is a TETFund intervention annually. This will boost the availability of AV resources while improving digital learning among students of the institutions.
2. The libraries should be more proactive in the promotion of library AV resources to the university community in order to increase awareness of AV resources among students and other library users, as well as train staff on how to provide technical support to library users.
3. The management of the universities should address the lingering problems facing the integration of AV resources in the library because it facilitates understanding, especially in a blended learning environment.

References

- Abubakar, T. A., Abdullah, A.-H., Ali, A. R., & Kabir, Z. M. (2018). Teachers' Preference on Application of Audio-visuals in Teaching Islamic Religious Studies in Secondary Schools: A Case Study of Katsina Metropolis, Nigeria. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8(4), 737–754. <https://doi.org/10.6007/ijarbss/v8-i4/4058>
- Andrew Fernando, Dewa Putu, A. T. (2020). Pengembangan Media Pembelajaran (1st Edisio). Yayasan Kita Menulis.
- Aloraini, S. (2012). The impact of using multimedia on students' academic achievement in the College of Education at King Saud University. *Journal of King Saud University - Educational Sciences and Islamic Studies*, 24 (2), 1-13.
- Berk, R. A. (2009). Multimedia teaching with video clips: TV, movies, YouTube, and mtvU in the college classroom. *International Journal of Technology in Teaching and Learning*, 5 (1), 1-21
- Chukwuemeka C. & Oluwabunmi, O. O. (2022). Availability and Utilization of Audio-Visuals for Teaching and Learning in Nigerian Universities: A Case Study. *Journal of Applied Information Science and Technology*, 15 (2)
- Dewi, P. C., Hudiyono, Y., & Mulawarman, W. G. (2018). Pengembangan Bahan Ajar Menulis Teks Prosedur Kompleks Dengan Model Pembelajaran Discovery Learning Menggunakan Media Audio Visual (Video) Di Kelas Xi Sma Negeri 1 Samarinda. *DIGLOSIA: Jurnal Kajian Bahasa, Sastra, Dan Pengajarannya*, 1(2), 101–112. <https://doi.org/10.30872/diglosia.v1i2.pp101-112>
- Indrawati, C. D. S., Ninghardjanti, P., Dirgatama, C. H. A., & Wirawan, A. W. (2022). The Effect of Practicum Learning Based Audiovisual on students' Learning Outcomes in Indonesian Vocational Secondary School. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 11(1), 403–408. <https://doi.org/10.11591/ijere.v11i1.21762>
- Isna Nadifah Nur Fauziah, Selly Ade Saputri, & Tin Rustini. (2023). Penggunaan Media Audio Visual Dalam Meningkatkan Hasil Belajar Pada Pelajaran Ilmu Pengetahuan Sosial Siswa

- Sekolah Dasar. Dirasah: *Jurnal Studi Ilmu Dan Manajemen Pendidikan Islam*, 6(1), 125–135. <https://doi.org/10.58401/dirasah.v6i1.789>
- Kay, R. H., LeSage, A., & Knaack, L. (2009). Exploring student and faculty perceptions of the use of multimedia in undergraduate teaching. *The Canadian Journal for the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, 1 (2), 1-21.
- Fetterman, D. M. (2016). The role of audio-visual resources in enhancing classroom learning. *Journal of Educational Technology*, 45(2), 123-135
- Kuma, R. (2018). Educational Technology and Multimedia. New Delhi: ABC Publishers
- Mayer, R. E. (2009). Multimedia learning (2nd ed.). Cambridge University Press.
- Natoli, C. (2011). The Importance of Audio-Visual Resources in Teaching and Learning. www.helium.com/channels/224-earlychildhood-edu.
- Ojobor, R. C., Babarinde, E. T. & Fagbemi, V. O. (2020). Audio-visual resources in library: An enhancing tool for effective teaching and learning in primary schools in Nsukka L.G.A. *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)* 4361. Retrieved from <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/>
- Onuoha, J. & Chukwueke, C. (2020). Availability and utilization of audio-visual resources for teaching and learning in Government Day Secondary School, Nukkai, Jalingo, Taraba State, Nigeria. *International Journal Dissemination*, 1 (2), 26-36
- Oyewale, G. M. J. O. (2021). The Use of Technology in Teaching and Learning of History in Secondary Schools. *American Journal of Multidisciplinary Research & Development (AJMRD)*, 03(06), 43–48. www.ajmrd.com
- Patil, V.G. (2012). Importance of audiovisual aids in teaching methodology. Retrieved from <http://www.articlebase.com/tutoring-article/importance-of-audio-visual-in-techingmethodology-3667855html> on November 11, 2025
- Rahmatullah, R., Inanna, I., & Ampa, A. T. (2020). Media Pembelajaran Audio Visual Berbasis Aplikasi Canva. *Jurnal Pendidikan Ekonomi Undiksha*, 12(2), 317–327
- Riyanto, N., & Asmara, A. P. (2018). Penilaian Kualitas Media Audio Visual Tentang Karakteristik Larutan Asam Basa Untuk Siswa Sma/Ma. *Jurnal Pendidikan Sains (Jps)*,
- Raudatussolihah, B. (2022). Pengembangan Teknologi Audio-Visual dalam Pembelajaran Bahasa Arab. *Education and Learning Journal*, 3(1), 53. <https://doi.org/10.33096/eljour.v3i1.150> 6(1), 73. <https://doi.org/10.26714/jps.6.1.2018.73> 85
- Wahlig, H (2012). Roles of visual aids in the classroom. Retrieved from http://www.ehow.com/list_6669336_roles-visual-aids-classroom.html on November 17, 2025